

Case report

Left Atrial Myxoma: A Rare Cause of Chronic Dyspnea ^{*}Corresponding author

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*Richmond Ronald Gomes, Associate Professor, Medicine, Ad-din Women's Medical College. Hospital.***Abstract**

Atrial myxomas are a rare phenomenon and although benign, primary neoplasms of the heart can be burdensome depending on their location. More than 90% are solitary and women are affected more than men. Clinical symptoms are caused through a variety of mechanisms including conduction disturbances, obstruction, and valvular interference. Sizes, location, mobility of the tumor and symptom development are strongly correlated and can almost always be detected by the use of echocardiography, magnetic resonance imaging or computed tomography. This is a case of a 45-year-old female with no significant past medical history presented to our facility with complaints of dyspnea on exertion, episodic palpitations and associated dizziness for three years. Transthoracic echocardiography revealed large left atrial myxoma with moderate pulmonary hypertension. After confirming the diagnosis of cardiac tumor we transferred the patient to a surgical centre for further treatment.

Key words: Atrial myxomas, conduction disturbances, valvular interference, transthoracic echocardiography**Introduction**

The most frequent benign tumor of the heart is myxomas and accounting in approximately 30% of all primary cardiac tumors [1]. 75% are located in the left atrium [2]. Myxoma is a benign polypoid neoplasm, usually originates from endocardial cells in the region of fossa ovalis and is attached to the interatrial septum. Myxomas are pedunculated, friable and appear as a soft, gelatinous, mucoid, usually gray-white mass often with areas of hemorrhage or thrombi. They are slowly growing and usually do not produce symptoms or signs until they enlarge. Their size, shape and texture can be quite varied. Myxomas may be smooth surfaced but are more often irregularly shaped or have the appearance of a "cluster of grapes". They are typically nonhomogeneous in texture with lucent centers or areas of calcification. Myxomas can be quite large, occupying most of the left atrium and resulting obstruction to left ventricular filling. The diagnosis can be established by the demonstration of a characteristic echo producing mass in the left atrium by two-dimensional (2D) echocardiography [3,4]. Although asymptomatic patients with myxomas have been reported, most present with one or more effects of a triad of constitutional, embolic and obstructive manifestations [5]. Typically, these large pedunculated tumors advance through and obstruct the atrioventricular valves during diastole and are expelled retrogradely into the atrium during systole. The most common clinical presentation mimics that of mitral valve disease [6], either stenosis due to tumor prolapse into mitral orifice or regurgitation due to tumor induced valve trauma. Manifestations include conduction

disturbances, obstruction, and valvular interference owing to symptoms including dyspnea, orthopnea, cough, edema and fatigue. Given that clinical symptoms overlap with congestive heart failure and other cardiac abnormalities, accurate diagnosis is imperative for appropriate treatment and prognosis. Most atrial myxomas are benign and can be removed by surgical resection [7,8].

Case report

A 45-year-old female with no significant past medical history and no comorbidities presented with complaints of episodic palpitation, dizziness and shortness of breath on exertion for three years. The patient developed the symptoms especially in sitting posture when raising from the bed in the early morning hours and get relieved when lying down. The symptoms were intermittent for a short period recently. Constitutional symptoms such as arthralgia, myalgia, and weight loss were also present.

Prior work-up of her symptoms with ETT and with holter monitoring showed no irregularities. On arrival, she was in no acute distress and her palpitations had subsided. Vitals that were obtained were largely unremarkable. Her ECG (Figure 1) showed nonspecific ST-T changes with no acute irregularity and laboratory testing was within normal limits except ESR was 85 mm in 1st hour. Chest X ray (figure 2) showed interstitial shadowing.

Figure 1 and figure 2: ECG showing nonspecific ST-T changes and Chest X ray showing interstitial shadowing.

Physical examination revealed mild clubbing and auscultatory findings were consistent with mitral valve stenosis and insufficiency. A loud first and second heart sound, low pitched “tumor plop”, a holosystolic murmur that was loudest at the apex and resembled mitral regurgitation and a mid diastolic murmur well noticed in the sitting position were the characteristic findings masquerading as Rheumatic mitral stenosis and regurgitation. She did not exhibit jugular venous distention or peripheral edema and other organ systems did not yield and irregularities. Transthoracic echocardiography revealed an in homogenous contractile oscillating mass (33 x 58 mm) was seen in LA attached to IAS frequently obstructing MV opening suggestive of LA myxoma, moderate TR with severe pulmonary hypertension with PASP 103 mm Hg (figure 3).

Figure 3: Transthoracic echocardiography showing an in homogenous contractile oscillating mass (33 x 58 mm) was seen in LA attached to IAS suggestive of LA myxoma.

Additional imaging studies including cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) were not obtained due to unavailability. She was given symptomatic treatment with small doses of diuretics and beta blockers such bisoprolol, symptom free thereafter and advised to avoid exertion. Since the age was advanced and well maintaining basic life style, surgical intervention was not preferred in this patient. Echocardiographic screening of family members revealed no abnormality.

Discussion

Cardiac myxoma represents 30-50% of all benign tumors, 25% of all tumors and cysts of heart, usually are solitary [9] and develop in the atria, 75% originating from the left atrium and 15- 20% from the right atrium. These tumors arise from or near the interatrial septum at the border of the fossa ovalis membrane and occur in all age groups, most frequently between the third and sixth decade. Myxomas are typically pedunculated with a stalk that is attached to the interatrial septum in fossa ovalis region. Women are more commonly affected and myxomas usually occur sporadically but there are also familiar forms. In about 20% cases, myxomas are

asymptomatic and are discovered as an incidental finding [10,11].

The cause of syndrome myxoma is unknown [12]. It has been proposed to result from a widespread abnormality resulting in excessive proliferation of certain mesenchymal cells and excessive glycosaminoglycans production by them. Most tumors are histologically benign and potentially lethal due to intra cavity or valvular obstruction, peripheral embolism and conduction disturbances. The association of constitutional symptoms is likely due to synthesis and secretion of interleukin-6.

Tumors of the heart commonly present with symptoms that correlate with the location, the degree of obstruction, and interference with heart valves or circulation. Clinical symptoms demonstrated in the literature include chest pain, dyspnea, and syncope but infrequently present with palpitations for an extended period of time [13-16]. Our patient had no past medical history and prior workup from an electrophysiological standpoint was within normal limits including ECG analysis and holter monitoring.

Left atrial myxomas prolapse to various degrees into mitral valve orifice, resulting in obstruction to AV (atrioventricular) blood flow and frequently, mitral regurgitation. The resultant signs and symptoms often mimic those of mitral valve disease [17], especially mitral stenosis. Symptoms of sudden in onset, intermittent and related to the patient’s body position [18], should raise the suspicion of left atrial myxoma. When atrial Myxomas obstruct the AV valves, the patient may experience dyspnea, dizziness or syncope when sitting or standing with alleviation of symptoms on lying down. Sudden death may also occur. The loud first heart sound that occurs in patients with left atrial Myxoma may be due to them late onset of mitral valve closure resulting from prolapsed of the tumor through the mitral valve and frequently split, with the second component corresponding to the expulsion of the tumor from the mitral orifice. In many cases, an early diastolic sound, termed a “tumor plop” can be identified and it is thought to be produced as the tumor strikes the endothelial wall or its excursion is abruptly halted. If the obstruction is incomplete, the tumor plop may be followed by a diastolic rumble. When the obstruction becomes more severe, cardiac output may fall precipitously.

Myxomas are polypoid, round, or oval. Their clinical features are determined by their location, size, and mobility of myxoma. In left-sided myxomas symptoms more frequently occur when the diameter is over 5 cm or when the tumor reaches about 70 grams. Clinical presentation is categorized in four general manifestations - systemic, embolic, cardiac manifestations and phenomena secondary to metastatic diseases. Symptoms range from non-specific constitutional to sudden cardiac death. Symptoms of intracardiac flow obstruction are the most commonly described

manifestation, occurring in more than 50% of persons with cardiac myxomas. Typically, patients show symptoms of left-sided heart failure (eg, dyspnea, orthopnea, or fatigue) or syncope. Right atrial myxomas can manifest with symptoms of right-sided heart failure (eg, systemic oedema or hepatomegaly). About 30-40% of individuals with cardiac myxomas experience embolic phenomena. Embolization appears to be much more likely in myxomas that are friable. Sites of embolization include the central nervous system (CNS), kidneys, extremities, and coronary arteries. Clinical manifestations of embolization are broad and depend on the tissues downstream of the embolus. Paradoxical embolism may occur in individuals with an anatomically patent foramen ovale [23 - 25]. Nonspecific constitutional symptoms have been reported in 20-60% of individuals with cardiac myxomas. Such symptoms may include fever, arthralgia, myalgia, and weight loss.

Given a typical presentation, Diagnosis with two-dimensional echocardiography is usually adequate with good sensitivity detecting 95% of Myxomas but we can complete the diagnosis with transesophageal echocardiography as a more sensitive method [19 - 21]. For diagnosis of cardiac tumors we can also use cardiac MRI, computer tomography (CT) and PET scan. Coronary angiography is used to exclude co-existing coronary artery disease in patients over 40 or 50 years of age, depending on the surgical centre 16,22. The ability to detect atrial myxoma of the heart by means of echocardiography was first reported more than two decades ago by Effort and Domani. 2D echocardiography is the non invasive procedure of choice for the diagnosis of left atrial myxoma. The virtual pathognomonic finding of an atrial myxoma is that of a large pedunculated tumor mass traversing through the AV valves in a to-and-fro motion. Large atrial myxomas have been classified by echo appearance as follows [26].

- Class I-small and prolapse through the mitral valve.
- Class II-small and non-prolapsing.
- Class III-large and prolapsing.
- Class IV-large and non-prolapsing.

Myxomas are mottled in appearance and in some atrial myxomas, areas of echo lucency corresponding to areas of hemorrhage within the tumor which are not seen in thrombi or infective lesions. Other loss. Laboratory findings may include elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (33%), normochromic anemia (15%), and thrombocytopenia (5%).

For recurrence of cardiac myxoma it is very important to know whether the myxoma is familial. The recurrence rate is 1-3% in patients with sporadic myxomas but 10-20% in patients with familial myxomas [27]. In patients with sporadic myxomas, incomplete excision is thought to be the most likely reason for tumor recurrence and clinical follow-up is recommended for individuals diagnosed with cardiac myxomas especially with familial cardiac myxomas.

When the diagnosis is confirmed, prompt resection is suggested to avoid the possibility of further manifestations including embolization or sudden cardiac death [28,29]. Outcomes are largely favorable with a mortality rate under 5% [27 - 29]; however, post-operative development of arrhythmias and atrioventricular conduction abnormalities have been reported in approximately 25% of patients [28]. Large size of myxoma together with location on posterior left atrial wall necessitates complete removal of the heart which was followed by "auto transplantation" i.e., reimplantation of the patient's excised heart. A cloth patch or parietal pericardium is used to close the surgical defect. Damaged valves may require annuloplasty or prosthetic replacement in case of prolapse of a tumor through the mitral or tricuspid valve resulting in the destruction of the annulus or valve leaflets.

Conclusion

This patient presented with long standing dyspnea on exertion and palpi-

tation. Imaging modalities including echocardiography, CT, and cardiac MRI are considered equally efficacious for the diagnosis of atrial tumors as they provide the location within the heart. Additional studies including angiography and biopsy are commonly required for further evaluation when surgery is planned. Surgical intervention consists of tumor resection and despite a low mortality rate, complications including arrhythmias and atrioventricular conduction delays are possible.

Conflict of interest

None declared

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